

Condensations of Urethane, Phenylurethane and Diphenylurethane with Resorcinol.

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Sen and Guha Sarkar succeeded in bringing about a condensation of salicylic ester with resorcinol and pyrogallol with the formation of benzoids (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 157). In elaboration of that work, Sen and Mukherji (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 557) successfully condensed resorcinol, dimethylaniline and diethyl-*m*-aminophenol with various aromatic and aliphatic esters and glycerides.

In the present investigation, the same reaction has been further extended to the condensation of urethane and substituted urethanes with resorcinol leading to the formation of pyronine dyes in which the hydrogen-atom attached to the central carbon atom has been replaced by an amino- or a substituted amino-group, the mechanism of the reaction being represented thus:—

The structure (Ia) for the urethane condensation product is supported by the following observations:—

(a) The compound gives coloured mono-potassium and mono-silver salts.

(b) When acetylated in alkaline solution by chloroacetyl chloride, it yields a monochloroacetyl derivative (only hydroxyl attacked). Structure (Ib) should have given a dichloroacetyl derivative.

(c) When acetylation is carried out by heating the compound with chloroacetyl chloride at its boiling point, a dichloroacetyl compound is formed (OH and NH_2 both attacked). Structure (Ib) should have given a trichloroacetyl derivative.

(d) When to a hot solution of the compound in alcohol mixed with a solution of sodium nitrite, dilute hydrochloric acid is dropped, nitrogen is evolved and the product that is formed is found to be free from nitrogen and on further crystallization from alcohol melts at 235° and is probably the expected isoeuxanthone (m.p. 243°).

It is remarkable that alkaline or acid hydrolytic agents such as alcoholic potash, strong hydrochloric acid or moderately strong sulphuric acid have no action on the compound, showing that the NH_2 -group in this configuration is quite stable. It may also be noted that the compound is insoluble in dilute acids.

When brominated, the urethane compound yields a tetrabromo-derivative, while the phenyl and diphenyl compounds yield dibromo-derivatives, all of which dye beautiful red shades on wool and silk.

In alkaline and alcoholic solutions, the condensation products of resorcinol with urethane and substituted urethanes exhibit moderate fluorescence (bluish-green), which is most marked in the case of the unsubstituted product. The urethane compound dyes golden yellow shade on wool and silk, which becomes slightly deeper (redder) as the hydrogen atoms in urethane are substituted by phenyl residues. Since the difference in the colour of the compounds is not more marked, the urethane and the monophenyl urethane condensation products appear also to have a quinonoid structure (Ia), like the diphenylurethane condensation product which admits of no other configuration but the quinonoid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

6-Hydroxy-9-aminofluorone (Ia).—Urethane (1 mol.) and resorcinol (2 mols.) were heated to 180° for 6 hours with zinc chloride as the condensing agent. The product was purified in the same way as resorcinolbenzein (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 557). It is a brownish-yellow powder, soluble in alcohol, acetone, glacial acetic acid, less so in benzene, ether and chloroform; insoluble in petroleum ether and toluene. Alkaline alcoholic and acetone solutions show green fluorescence. It dyes golden yellow shades on wool and silk and softens at 210°; yield 85 per cent. (Found: N, 5.95. $C_{13}H_9ON_3$ requires, N, 6.16 per cent.).

Monopotassium Derivative.—Prepared as usual. (Found: K, 14.7. $C_{13}H_9O_3NK$ requires K, 14.7 per cent.).

Monosilver derivative.—Prepared from the K-derivative by the addition of silver nitrate. (Found: Ag, 32.2. $C_{13}H_9O_3NAg$ requires Ag, 32.3 per cent.).

Monochloroacetyl Derivative.—Prepared by shaking the alkaline solution with the addition of chloroacetyl chloride drop by drop till acid. Recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, it softens at 194°. (Found: Cl, 11.55. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4NCl$ requires Cl, 11.69 per cent.).

Dichloroacetyl Derivative.—Prepared by boiling 6-hydroxy-9-aminofluorone with excess of chloroacetyl chloride under an air condenser. Purified from alcohol and then from glacial acetic acid m.p. 150°. (Found: Cl, 18.20. $C_{17}H_{11}O_5NCl_2$ requires Cl, 18.70 per cent.).

Tetrabromo Derivative.—Prepared by bromination in alcoholic solution and recrystallisation from alcohol. It decompose at 250°. (Found: Br, 57.9. $C_{13}H_9O_3NBr_4$ requires Br, 58.9 per cent.).

6-Hydroxy 9-phenylaminofluorone.—Prepared from phenylurethane and resorcinol. Brownish-yellow powder. Softens at 195°. Solubility similar to 6-hydroxy-9-aminofluorone. Dyes slightly redder shades. Alkaline and alcoholic solutions show bluish-green fluorescence. Yield 80%, (Found: N, 4.5. $C_{19}H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 4.62 per cent.).

Dibromo-derivative.—Prepared by brominating the above. Red powder decomposing at 290°. Dyes wool and silk red shades.

6-Hydroxy-9-iphenylaminofluorone.—Prepared from diphenyl urethane and resorcinol. Brownish-yellow powder softens at 275°. Dyes wool and silk reddish-brown shades. Alkaline and alcoholic solutions show blue fluorescence. Yield 80 per cent. (Found: N, 3.59. $C_{25}H_{17}O_3N$ requires N, 3.69 per cent.).

*Dibromo-derivative*₂—Prepared by brominating the above compound in alcoholic solution. Red powder, decomposes at 220°. Dyes wool and silk bright red shades. (Found: Br, 29·4. $C_{25}H_{17}O_3NBr_2$ requires Br, 29·9 per cent.).

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